

Postharvest technology

Multipurpose yard-drying implement for rice

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Despite the introduction of mechanical dryers for drying parboiled rice, yard drying is still practiced in many countries because of the scarcity of electricity and for economic reasons. Sunshine and human labor are readily available most of the year in tropical countries. Yard drying is practical, but it causes nonuniform drying and cracks to form in the grain due to continuous exposure to the sun.

In the existing system of yard drying, different types of wooden boards are used for spreading, combing, turning, and floor drying. This requires several laborers to work together. Due to the intensity of sunshine, the laborers must rest frequently as a group, resulting in intermittent turning of the rice. The grain exposed to the sun during these rest periods over-dries, resulting in nonuniform drying.

The solution to this problem is to continuously turn the rice, as in a mechanical dryer, while still using the available labor and solar energy. We developed a multipurpose yard-drying implement (MYDI) to achieve this goal (Fig. 1). It has a simple frame made of angle iron and flats that is mounted on two heavy duty bicycle wheels. The front swing of the MYDI is pinned with three kinds of wooden boards, used one at a time (Fig. 2). The toothed board is used for combing and leveling, the triangular board for floor drying, and the angular board for turning the rice. Conventional boards are used for spreading and collection, which involve only a few minutes of effort.

Only one laborer is needed at a time to operate the MYDI, so the others can rest while not working. Thus, the MYDI is operated continuously. The boards are interchanged as required.

On cloudy days and in winter, parboiled rice is dried to a moisture content where it is ready for milling in 1 d. The MYDI reduces drying time and ensures uniform drying.

On normal sunny days in southern India, ambient air temperature goes above 30 °C.

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1. Multipurpose yard-drying implement (MYDI) for rice.

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2. The three kinds of wooden boards attached to the MYDI.

Continuing the drying beyond the critical moisture of 16-18% causes cracks to form in the grain, resulting in many broken during milling. With the MYDI, both the drying rate is increased and the critical moisture is reached uniformly in all grain after about 4-4.5 h of drying. At this stage, rice is heaped and covered with gunny sacks or tarpaulin for tempering. The laborers may rest during this process while the yard floor absorbs the heat, which is used during the second stage of drying. After 2-2.5 h, the rice is again spread out for about 45 min to 1 h by continuous turning with the MYDI to attain the 14% moisture content that is usually desirable for milling.

The MYDI system provides higher head rice yield and fewer broken (about 5%) compared with the conventional system, which causes broken of more than 20%. The MYDI helps to increase labor productivity and reduces drudgery. It may also be used, with modifications in the wooden

boards, for other grains that are dried in the yard.

A MYDI and 3 persons are needed for drying 5 t of parboiled rice. One unit costs about US\$80 and can be easily fabricated, repaired, and maintained. Artisans who make conventional boards can make the wooden boards used in the MYDI. ■

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